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ANALYSIS OF DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE TRAIN SAFETY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM AT STATIONS

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Annotation: *JSC “Uzbekiston Temir Yullari”, since its formation on November 7, 1994, has been the most important structural link in the formation and development of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for more than 20 years. Sustainable development, stability, introduction of innovative technologies, dynamic increase in the rates of economic and industrial growth of the enterprises of “Uzbekiston Temir Yullari” JSC create favorable conditions for the development of the transport industry and the entire economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan as a whole.*

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Throughout the existence and functioning of railway transport works in close connection with other branches of the national economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. One of its main tasks is to meet the needs of the economy in providing timely cargo and passenger transportation. The work in this direction is carried out in various aspects and is aimed at ensuring the safe maximum possible throughput and carrying capacity of the railway network of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Traffic safety is a comprehensive indicator reflecting the level of development of technique, technology, labor organization, management and economics of railway transport. The traffic safety management system is a set of

interrelated technical means and technical personnel, the functioning of which is aimed at solving one task — ensuring the regulatory level of transportation safety [1].

Effective security management cannot be carried out without automating the execution of a number of important functions. Automated control systems should automate the calculation of train safety indicators and the functioning of technical means, as well as operational control of the current maintenance of the track. Today there are several main directions of automation of traffic safety tasks:

- usage of diagnostic complexes for monitoring the condition of technical means, accounting and analysis of their failures and refusals;
- analysis of statistics and conditions of occurrence of cases of marriage, wrecks and accidents;
- automation of shunting and train work in order to prevent accidents and cases of marriage

The strategy for the development of control systems and ensuring the safety of train traffic at stations provides for the creation of an integrated system based on:

- a microprocessor control system for stations and a site based on open-source computing tools, as well as microprocessor and relay-processor systems, taking into account self-diagnosis and redundancy;
- interconnected arms of dispatching, engineering and management personnel on a single hardware platform;
- variants of modifications of the interval control system using a digital radio channel as a backup channel for transmitting-responsible-information.
- security, management, diagnostics and decoding of trip results;
- auto-locking systems with centralized equipment placement, tonal rail circuits and redundant information transmission channels designed for interval

regulation of train traffic on stages with the circulation of freight, passenger and high-speed trains;

- control of the technical condition of the rolling stock in the process of movement.

The implemented components of the integrated system should ensure the safety of trains in high-speed, passenger and freight traffic on the basis of modern technologies. All software-controlled microprocessor systems of railway transport must be checked for functional safety, the absence of undeclared capabilities and unauthorized access. Circuit solutions and software of such systems already at the design stage should take into account the possibility of various kinds of cyber attacks.

In addition, there is a mandatory check of microprocessor technical means of controlling motion processes for resistance to electromagnetic radiation, which will increase their reliability and minimize the possibility of negative influence [9].

The domestic system of management and ensuring the safety of train traffic covers the entire complex of related technological processes of track and energy management, telecommunications and communication systems, repair and restoration work.

For the further development of the infrastructure and rolling stock of the company, “Uzbekiston Temir Yullari” JSC provides:

- automation of the train control function;
- expansion of safety functions of station control systems at marshalling yards;
- development and implementation of innovative technologies;
- application of modern information systems and digital communication systems;
- further development of logistics centers, organization on their basis of effective interaction with other modes of transport;

- introduction of customer interaction technologies by expanding the use of interactive services;

To sum up the implementation, the creation of a unified transport network of railways of the Republic of Uzbekistan will be achieved, the infrastructure of all regions of the country will be evenly developed, the rolling stock base will be updated, conditions for stable growth of the state economy will be created. The reform of the industry will ensure the optimization of its structure and the inflow of investments for the modernization and expansion of the railway network. As a result of the implementation of the above works, the mobility of the population will be increased [5].

In order to ensure the safety of train traffic at stations and reduce the impact of failures of railway infrastructure facilities, "Russian Railways" uses an automated system for conducting monthly commission inspection reports (AS MCI). The main goals of creating an automated system:

- automation of document flow in the process of organizing and conducting a monthly commission inspection of the station;
- systematization of data on identified malfunctions of technical devices of the station for the purpose of processing for the analysis of the state of train safety;
- increasing the level of control over the timeliness and quality of elimination of identified malfunctions of the station's technical devices;
- improving the quality of the monthly commission inspection of the station;
- increasing the level of responsibility of station managers and managers of road enterprises for the condition of the station's technical devices.

The figure shows a diagram of the interaction of user categories with the AS of the MCI. The data on monthly commission inspections of the AS MCI are further taken into account in the integrated automated system of accounting, control, elimination of failures of technical means and analysis of their reliability [4].

Fig. 1 Diagram of the interaction of user categories with AS MCI

The experience of the European Union States shows that by the early 1990s, the development of a unified European railway network depended on solving the following problems in the field of interoperability and safety in the organization of international transportation [8]:

- there were more than 20 different and incompatible train control systems in operation;
- each country had its own rules for the operation of railways, some of them even contradicted each other;
- each country had its own national requirements for safety certification;
- each country used its own systems of training and licensing of machinists;
- five different traction power supply systems were used;
- eight different and incompatible communication and radio communication systems were used;

- almost every country has its own language.

These problems and their consequences (downtime at borders, significant costs and, as a result, high tariffs) sharply reduced the competitiveness and attractiveness of rail transport compared to road transport for the transportation of passengers and cargo in international traffic [7]. The way out of this situation was the creation of a single European system that ensures interoperability and safety of railway traffic in international traffic, which was conditioned by the coordination of the Missions, Goals and Policies of national railway administrations in the field of safety [2]. On this basis, it was possible to form the key elements of the new system:

- security design bodies;
- regulatory and advisory bodies;
- regulatory framework of safety;
- system and technical solutions.

Safety design bodies are represented by the European institutes CENELEC⁴, ERRI⁵, IRSE⁶ and others, associations of manufacturers and users of railway technologies (UNIFE⁷, UNISIG⁸, EIM⁹, etc.), as well as large companies and other organizations. The organizational structure of the ERA Security Management is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Organizational structure of the European Railway Agency Safety Management

The main regulatory document – the "top-level" document regulating the issues of traffic safety on the railways of the EU Member States is the Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council of the EU 2004/49/EU "On the safety of Community railways", which provides for the introduction of [3]:

- uniform safety rules for all participating States based on common safety and interoperability standards;
- a unified procedure for training, certification and admission to work of personnel

The modern approach to ensuring traffic safety on the railways of developed countries is to use a systematic approach in which technology plays an important, but not the only role. In conditions of resource scarcity, it is more preferable to invest in systemic measures that contribute to achieving a high level of manageability of security-related processes [6].

The developed systems cover most issues of prevention of traffic safety violations. An integrated approach to ensuring safety at the station is focused primarily on strict compliance with the technology of the station according to the regulations adopted in the industry. Multilateral data collection using the listed automated systems allows monitoring the current state of security at stations and timely taking adequate measures to prevent security breaches.

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